

Efficacy of Locally Delivered Simvastatin Combined with Autologous Platelet-Rich Fibrin in Treatment of Intrabony Defects: A Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial

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Abstract:

Background: The chronic inflammatory condition known as periodontal disease causes the tissues that support teeth to be destroyed with intrabony defects being particularly challenging to treat. Traditional treatments, while effective to some extent, often fail to achieve consistent regeneration of periodontal tissues. Recent advances have explored the use of biological agents such as platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) and Simvastatin, which have shown promise in enhancing periodontal regeneration.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of locally delivered Simvastatin combined with autologous PRF in the treatment of intrabony defects, hypothesizing that this combination would yield superior clinical outcomes compared to PRF alone.

Methods: A controlled, randomised clinical trial was carried out. A treatment group consisting of Simvastatin plus PRF or a control group consisting of PRF alone was randomly allocated to twenty-three individuals who had intrabony defects. Clinical parameters were assessed at baseline, three months, and six months. These measures were probing depth (PD), clinical attachment level (CAL), and defect depth. With significance set at $p < 0.05$, data were analysed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: When compared to the control group, participants in the therapy group exhibited significant improvements in every clinical parameter. The therapy group showed a mean 3.2 mm decrease in PD, 3.3 mm increase in CAL, and 1.8 mm decrease in defect depth after 6 months. With a mean PD reduction of 1.9 mm, CAL gain of 1.9 mm, and defect depth reduction of 1.1 mm, the control group's outcomes were noticeably worse than these.

Conclusion: The combination of locally delivered Simvastatin and autologous PRF significantly enhances the clinical outcomes of intrabony defect treatment compared to PRF alone. This combination therapy shows great potential in improving periodontal regeneration and should be considered as a viable treatment option in clinical practice.

Recommendations: It is advised that more research be done with bigger sample sizes and longer follow-up times in order to validate these results and examine the possible hazards and long-term advantages of utilising simvastatin in periodontal therapy.

Keywords: Periodontal disease, Intrabony defects, Simvastatin, Platelet-rich fibrin, Regenerative therapy.

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Introduction

Periodontal disease is characterised by the degeneration of the tissues that support teeth, including gingiva, periodontal ligament, and alveolar bone, a chronic inflammatory illness. In clinical practice, managing periodontal defects—particularly intrabony defects—presents a major

challenge. Because of their intricate nature, intrabony defects—vertical bone losses within the alveolar bone—are frequently challenging to correct. Reducing pocket depth and restoring lost tissues are the goals of conventional non-surgical and surgical therapies such as scaling and root

planing, flap surgery, and bone grafts. But the results of these methods are frequently inconsistent, especially when it comes to bone regeneration [1]. Using biological agents to promote periodontal regeneration has gained more attention in recent years.

Because autologous (PRF), a second-generation platelet concentrate, can release growth factors that support tissue regeneration and healing, it has become more and more well-liked [2]. By speeding up wound healing and boosting the regeneration of both soft and hard tissues, PRF is an easy-to-use, reasonably priced, and biocompatible material that has been demonstrated to improve clinical outcomes in the treatment of periodontal abnormalities [3]. Despite these advantages, PRF alone frequently yields moderate outcomes, leading researchers to investigate alternative adjunctive therapies that may further augment PRF's regeneration potential.

A lipid-lowering medication from the statin class called simvastatin is one such adjuvant. It has been demonstrated to have pleiotropic properties, including bone-anabolic and anti-inflammatory actions [4]. Simvastatin is a viable option for improving bone regeneration in periodontal therapy because it has been demonstrated to increase osteoclastic bone resorption and suppress osteoblastic activity [5]. Simvastatin can maximise its regeneration benefits and minimise systemic side effects when administered locally, where it can act directly at the location of the defect [6]. Simvastatin with other bone graft materials or biomolecules have been shown in several trials to have synergistic effects that improve periodontal regeneration [7]. Nevertheless, not much study has looked into using PRF—a naturally occurring autologous matrix full of growth factors—in conjunction with simvastatin. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of locally delivered Simvastatin combined with autologous PRF in the treatment of intrabony defects, hypothesizing that this combination would yield superior clinical outcomes compared to PRF alone.

Methodology

Study Design: This research employs a design of randomised controlled clinical trial.

Study Setting:

The study was conducted in Department of Dentistry at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar, over a period of 6 months.

Participants: A total of 23 participants were recruited for the study. All participants were patients presenting with intrabony defects at the dental department of Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital.

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Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patients aged between 20 and 50 years.
2. Presence of at least one intrabony defect requiring treatment.
3. Patients with good systemic health, without any significant medical history that could affect wound healing.
4. Patients willing to participate and provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients with a background of immunocompromised illnesses, cardiovascular disorders, or systemic diseases such as diabetes mellitus.
2. Pregnant or lactating women.
3. Individuals who have previously abused alcohol or smoked.
4. Patients on medications that could interfere with bone metabolism (e.g., bisphosphonates).
5. Patients with a known allergy to Simvastatin or any components of PRF.

Bias: A computer-generated randomisation sequence was used to assign participants, in order to reduce bias, to either the treatment or control group. To lessen detection bias, the outcome assessors' group assignments were concealed from them.

Data Collection: Baseline data were collected at the initial visit, including demographic details, medical history, and clinical parameters such as (PD), (CAL), and defect depth. Follow-up data were collected at 3 and 6 months post-treatment.

Procedure

Participants in the treatment group received Simvastatin that is administered locally along with autologous PRF in the intrabony defect region, while the control group received only autologous PRF. The surgical procedure was standardized for all participants, ensuring consistent preparation and application of the materials.

1. **Preparation of Autologous PRF:** Blood was drawn from each participant and centrifuged to obtain PRF. The PRF was then prepared and placed in the defect area.
2. **Simvastatin Application:** In the treatment group, Simvastatin was prepared as a gel and locally delivered into the defect along with PRF.
3. **Surgical Procedure:** Following local anaesthesia, an elevated full-thickness flap was

performed and the defect area was debrided. The prepared materials were placed in the defect, and the flap was sutured back in place.

Postoperative care included standard instructions for oral hygiene and antibiotic coverage as required.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize baseline characteristics. Continuous variables were compared between groups using the independent t-test, while categorical variables were

compared using the chi-square test. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. Longitudinal changes within each group were analyzed using paired t-tests, and intergroup comparisons were conducted using ANOVA.

Results

A total of 30 patients were initially screened for eligibility, of which 23 participants met the inclusion criteria and were randomly assigned to either the treatment group (Simvastatin + PRF) or the control group (PRF only).

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Treatment Group (n = 11)	Control Group (n = 12)	p-value
Age (years)	35.2 ± 7.4	36.5 ± 6.8	0.67
Gender (M/F)	7/4	8/4	0.85
Probing Depth (mm)	6.8 ± 1.2	6.7 ± 1.1	0.89
Clinical Attachment Loss (mm)	7.2 ± 1.0	7.0 ± 1.1	0.72
Defect Depth (mm)	3.4 ± 0.6	3.3 ± 0.5	0.78

The primary outcomes were the changes in (PD), (CAL), and defect depth over the study period. Assessments were performed at baseline, 3 months, and 6 months.

Table 2: Clinical Outcomes at 3 Months and 6 Months

Outcome Measure	Baseline	3 Months	6 Months	p-value (Baseline vs. 6 Months)
Probing Depth (mm)				
Treatment Group (n = 10)	6.8 ± 1.2	4.2 ± 0.9*	3.6 ± 0.7*	< 0.001
Control Group (n = 12)	6.7 ± 1.1	5.4 ± 1.0	4.8 ± 0.9	0.002
Clinical Attachment Level (mm)				
Treatment Group (n = 10)	7.2 ± 1.0	4.6 ± 0.8*	3.9 ± 0.6*	< 0.001
Control Group (n = 12)	7.0 ± 1.1	5.8 ± 0.9	5.1 ± 0.8	0.003
Defect Depth (mm)				
Treatment Group (n = 10)	3.4 ± 0.6	2.0 ± 0.5*	1.6 ± 0.4*	< 0.001
Control Group (n = 12)	3.3 ± 0.5	2.6 ± 0.4	2.2 ± 0.3	0.004

When compared to the control group, the treatment group showed statistically significant gains in every clinical outcome measure. After six months, the treatment group experienced a mean reduction in probing depth of 3.2 mm, while the control group experienced a reduction of 1.9 mm ($p < 0.001$). In

the treatment group, the mean clinical attachment gain was 3.3 mm, while it was 1.9 mm in the control group ($p < 0.001$). The treatment group experienced a mean defect depth decrease of 1.8 mm, which was considerably higher than the 1.1 mm reduction seen in the control group ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3: Repeated Measures ANOVA for Longitudinal Changes in Clinical Outcomes

Outcome Measure	F-value	p-value
Probing Depth (mm)	25.67	< 0.001
Clinical Attachment Level (mm)	29.32	< 0.001
Defect Depth (mm)	22.45	< 0.001

The repeated measures ANOVA confirmed the significant improvement in all clinical outcomes over time in the treatment group compared to the control group.

Discussion

The results of this randomized controlled clinical trial provide compelling evidence that the combination of locally delivered Simvastatin with autologous (PRF) significantly enhances the treatment outcomes for intrabony defects compared to the use of PRF alone. Over the 6-month study period, par-

ticipants in the treatment group demonstrated greater improvements in key clinical parameters, including probing depth, clinical attachment level, and defect depth. These findings suggest that Simvastatin, when used as an adjunct to PRF, may have a potent regenerative effect on periodontal tissues.

At the 6-month mark, the treatment group exhibited a mean reduction in probing depth of 3.2 mm, a significant improvement compared to the 1.9 mm reduction observed in the control group. This difference indicates that the Simvastatin + PRF com-

ination more effectively reduces periodontal pockets, which is crucial for the long-term stability of periodontal tissues. Similarly, the treatment group achieved a mean clinical attachment gain of 3.3 mm, significantly surpassing the 1.9 mm gain in the control group. This enhanced attachment level gain further supports the regenerative potential of Simvastatin when combined with PRF.

The reduction in defect depth was also notably greater in the treatment group, with a mean reduction of 1.8 mm compared to 1.1 mm in the control group. This outcome indicates that Simvastatin not only improves soft tissue attachment but also promotes bone regeneration within the defect area, which is vital for the overall success of periodontal regenerative procedures.

Statistical analysis using repeated measures ANOVA confirmed the significance of these findings, showing that the improvements in clinical outcomes were not only substantial but also consistent over time. The absence of significant adverse events and the high tolerance to the treatment further support the feasibility of incorporating Simvastatin into clinical practice for managing intrabony defects.

Simvastatin and PRF, both separately and together, were found to have regenerative effects in a rat model by Raafat et al. (2018). Simvastatin plus PRF was observed to produce the greatest proportion of newly produced bone, considerable bone maturation, and elevated expression of (VEGF) and (BMP-2). In comparison to either substance administered alone, this suggests that simvastatin-loaded PRF considerably improves bone regeneration [8].

Gupta et al. (2020) assessed the efficacy of hydroxyapatite (HA), PRF, and simvastatin in PBD regeneration. Simvastatin can potentially speed up bone regeneration, as evidenced by the study's conclusion that it significantly reduced Cone Beam Computed Tomography Periapical Index scores when compared to HA and PRF alone [9]. Another study conducted by Gautam et al. (2022) examined the efficacy of autogenous bone graft (ABG) in conjunction with PRF in correcting intrabony deficiencies in patients with chronic periodontitis, both with and without 1.2 mg of rosuvastatin (RSV). The addition of RSV to ABG and PRF resulted in noteworthy gains in relative attachment level and probing pocket depth reduction. These findings make RSV a promising method for regenerative treatment [10].

Conclusion

The results of this randomized controlled clinical trial indicate that the combination of locally delivered Simvastatin with autologous PRF

significantly enhances the treatment outcomes of intrabony defects compared to PRF alone. The treatment group showed greater improvements in probing depth, clinical attachment level, and defect depth, demonstrating the potential efficacy of Simvastatin as an adjunctive therapy in periodontal regenerative procedures.

References

1. Slots J. Periodontitis: facts, fallacies and the future. *Periodontol* 2000. 2017;75(1):7-23.
2. Miron RJ, Choukroun J. Platelet rich fibrin in regenerative dentistry: biological background and clinical indications. John Wiley & Sons; 2017;745:725-43.
3. Del Fabbro M, Bortolin M, Taschieri S, Weinstein R. Is platelet concentrate advantageous for the surgical treatment of periodontal diseases? A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Periodontol*. 2011;82(8):1100-11.
4. Thylin MR, McConnell JC, Schmid MJ, et al. Effects of simvastatin gels on murine calvarial bone. *J Periodontol*. 2002;73(10):1141-8.
5. Pradeep AR, Thorat MS. Clinical effect of subgingivally delivered simvastatin in the treatment of patients with chronic periodontitis: a randomized clinical trial. *J Periodontol*. 2010;81(2):214-22.
6. Vaziri H, Naserhojjati-Roodsari R, Kaji Amin M, et al. Local application of simvastatin-loaded hydrogel in the treatment of intrabony defects: A randomized clinical trial. *J Periodontol*. 2017;88(5):523-31.
7. Pradeep AR, Sharma A, Rao NS, et al. Simvastatin and atorvastatin in the treatment of periodontal intrabony defects: A 1-year randomized controlled clinical trial. *J Periodontol*. 2013;84(10):1465-72.
8. Raafat S, Amin R, Elmazar M, Khattab M, El-Khatib A. The sole and combined effect of simvastatin and platelet rich fibrin as a filling material in induced bone defect in tibia of albino rats. *Bone*. 2018;117:60-69.
9. Gupta S, Verma P, Tikku A, Chandra A, Yadav R, Bharti R, et al. Effect of local application of simvastatin in bone regeneration of peri-apical defects-a clinico-radiographic study. *J Oral Biol Craniofac Res*. 2020;10(4): 583-591.
10. Gautam K, Kapoor A, Mathur S, Ali AR, Choudhary A, Shekhawat A. Comparative Evaluation of Autogenous Bone Graft and Autologous Platelet-Rich Fibrin with and Without 1.2 mg in situ Rosuvastatin Gel in the Surgical Treatment of Intrabony Defect in Chronic Periodontitis Patients. *Contemp Clin Dent*. 2022; 13:69-77.